

Design of growth-coupled measurements of transcription factor function

Gene circuit for transcription factor function

A proposal for onboarding Transcription Factors to the protein sequence-to-function measurement platform.

- Uses a gene circuit to tie transcription factor activity to bacterial cell growth
- Calibration variants span the dynamic range of activity enable quantitative function measurements
- First dataset collection will focus on RamR, LacI and TetR transcription factor families.

This document was created as a part of the Pooled, Growth-Based Assays for Protein Function Measurements pipeline¹ for Align to Innovate's Open Dataset Initiative. Align to Innovate is a non-profit research organization operating under open science principles with the goal of improving science research with programmable experiments. The Open Datasets Initiative is working to accelerate community-driven science with the use of automated labs to pioneer robust data collection methods and curated, high-fidelity, public biological datasets amenable to machine learning. This work was supported by Align to Innovate's Open Datasets Initiative which receives philanthropic funding in part from Griffin Catalyst.

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Context, Significance, and Impact

Transcription factors are crucial in scientific research and medicine due to their role in synthetic biology^{2,3}, widespread structural characteristics^{4,5}, and clinical importance, including studies on microbial antibiotic resistance^{6,7}.

The proposed transcription factor assay will be adaptable to

various TF functions, starting with data generation to predict a TF's repression ability and how TF mutations affect repression. We will measure sequence libraries with variations in both TF and operator sequences, focusing on the TF (e.g., five different operator sequences paired with around 30,000 different TF sequences).

Transcription Factor Circuit

In TF circuits, the TF is expressed from the Gene of Interest (GOI) region of the plasmid and interacts with the binding sequence in the circuit region of the plasmid to activate or repress gene expression (Fig. B1).

The selection cassette region of the plasmid used for initial data collection (Fig. B2) contains promoter and downstream operator regions. Initial targets will explore repression systems using the mechanism illustrated in Figure B1.

Proposed Hosts and Plasmids

The *E. Coli* strain MG1655 was chosen due to its relatively high transformation efficiency, and the availability of MG1655-derived strains with knockouts for many of the TFs planned for the pilot-scale and full-scale data collection (e.g., LacI).

Initial plasmid designs for the TF assay are given below. This includes one plasmid for each of the proposed Ab^R genes:

Link to Benchling for plasmid with Ab^R = TetA: <https://benchling.com/s/seq-bZBYSd4w2iEE5Rku1mN2?m=sim-3eW5WQJqTISH5xFal6Ra>

Link to Benchling for plasmid with Ab^R = Zeocin resistance: <https://benchling.com/s/seq-USOfsnvFEEPIfPfb2GLk?m=sim-gCuYngDEkHq2bilbY7h2>

Proposed Controls for Assay Development

Two well-characterized proteins, RamR (Uniprot ID: A0A0F6AY66) and LacI (Uniprot ID: P03023), will be used to ensure our methods align with established data. LacI is chosen due to its known structure in complex with DNA⁸ and engineered variants recognizing orthogonal operators^{9,10}. RamR is selected for its engineered variants with altered ligand specificity¹¹, which can be linked to DNA binding domain variants binding orthogonal operators.

Additionally, the TF team (co-lead by Simon d'Oelsnitz at Harvard and David Ross at NIST) has existing datasets on the LacI¹² and RamR (unpublished) transcriptional repressors, which will be the first two proteins tested in the growth-based assay. This data includes repression strength of >50,000 protein variants for the WT operator, as well as induction data (LacI: IPTG, RamR: 1SP/1RP/DHIQ) for all protein variants. Some of these protein variants have mutations in the DNA-binding domain that will be targeted for mutagenesis in the proposed experiments. The TF team has in-house, unpublished data on WT RamR's ability to repress promoters with single or double mutations in RamR operators, which will guide operator design for the proposed experiments.

Stage 1 - Development and Tuning

For the TF dataset in Stage 1, tuning sequences listed in Table B1 will be used. Various concentrations of inducers (additives) will modulate the interaction between the TFs and their operators with these sequences to cover the desired assay range. This approach allows sampling a wide range of functions with a single genotype per TF, minimizing the cloning needed for the initial tuning step.

Methods for the tuning step are as follows:

1. Use general flow cytometry in the [Singleplex Assay for Function Measurements protocol](#)¹³ to measure the

Operator (action site)	Protease variant (GOI)	Expected activity
Oid	WT TEV	High activity
Oramr	TEV2	Low activity

Table B1: The operator and TF combinations that will be used.

function for each tuning sequence. The plate diagram for this step is described in Figure B3. The plate layout will have an inducer concentration gradient along each row, with a maximum concentration [5000 umol/L isopropyl β-d-1-thiogalactopyranoside (IPTG) for LacI; 4000 umol/L tetrahydropapaverine (THP) for RamR] in column 12 and zero inducer in column 1. The inducer concentration gradient will have a 2-fold difference between adjacent wells. Rows A and H in the plate will be reserved for blanks and calibration beads needed for the flow cytometry measurements and during cell growth those rows will contain plain media (Fig. B3).

2. To measure the fitness for each tuning sequence (at each antibiotic concentration and each inducer concentration), the [Singleplex Assay for Fitness Measurements protocol](#)¹⁴ will be used with the plate layout shown in Figure B4. The plate layout will have a 2D, inducer x antibiotic, concentration gradient, with different antibiotic concentrations in each column and different inducer concentration in each row. Both concentration gradients will have a 2-fold difference between adjacent wells. The maximum antibiotic concentration will be either 10 ug/mL tetracycline (Tet) or 400 ug/mL zeocin (Zeo). The maximum inducer concentration will be chosen based on previous function measurements to optimally span the available function range. Two replicates will be measured, one on each half of the plate (Fig. B4).

Figure B3: Plate map for the singleplex function assay used during Stage 1.

Figure B4: Plate map for the singleplex fitness assay used during Stage 1.

Stage 2 - Normalization and Calibration Controls

For the TF dataset, in Stage 2, the candidate normalization and calibration controls will be as listed in [Table B2](#). The candidate normalization controls include a mutated variant of LacI with two early stop codons (L6*/Y12*), paired with the O3 operator and a mutated variant of RamR with two early stop codons (K11*/E16*), paired with the WT operator. These TF variants, due to early stop codons, should not repress, producing an «always-on» phenotype needed for normalization. Each candidate normalization sequence will be constructed, plated, and tested by picking three colonies for each.

For the fitness measurement of the normalization sequences for the TF dataset, the plate layout shown in [Figure B5](#) will be used. The plate layout has two antibiotic concentration gradients, one to be measured with an inducer (IPTG or THP), and the other without an inducer. The two gradients will be pipetted in opposite directions to reduce effects from differences in position within the plate. For samples with inducers, the same concentration will be used in all wells (5000 umol/L IPTG or 4000 umol/L THP). These are the same inducers, and at the same concentrations, that will be used in the pooled assay.

The plate layout shown in [Figure B6](#) will be used for the function

Operator (action site)	Protease variant (GOI)	Expected activity	Type of control
Olaci (O3)	LacI-L6*/Y12*	High signal (low repression)	Normalization
WT Oramr	RamR-K11*/E16*	High signal (low repression)	Normalization
Olaci (O1, O2, O3 and Oid)	LacI-S28R and LacI-V80D	Spanning >3 orders of magnitude	Calibration
Olaci (Oggg, Ogga, Oga, Ota, or Oggg)	LacI-(KQR, AAR, YAN, AQR)	Spanning >3 orders of magnitude	Calibration
Oramr (wt, t2a, t6a, and g5c)	RamR-S7F and RamR-D9H	Spanning >3 orders of magnitude	Calibration

Table B2: TF and operator sequence pair candidates for developing normalization and calibration controls.

measurement of the calibration sequences for the TF dataset. The plate layout contains each calibration sequence with and without an inducer. For samples with the inducer, the same concentration will be used in all wells (5000 umol/L IPTG or 4000 umol/L THP). These are the same inducers, at the same concentrations, that will be used in the pooled assay.

The fitness of some of the calibration sequences will be measured using the [Singleplex Assay for Fitness Measurements protocol](#)⁴. For those measurements, the plate layout in [Figure B7](#) will be used.

Figure B5: Plate map for the singleplex fitness assay used for normalization controls during Stage 2.

Pilot-Scale Collection: RamR, LacI, and TetR

During the pilot scale collection, three separate libraries will be run for RamR, LacI, and TetR. Each library will contain five operators (binding-site sequences), each paired with approximately 30,000 TF sequence variants (total diversity of each library $\sim 150k$). This split is chosen to maximize TF diversity, as the goal of the eventual predictive model will be to design the best TF for a given operator sequence. All three libraries will be measured in a single run using the pooled, growth-based assay protocol¹⁵. The layout for the plate shown in Figure B8 will be used.

The ultimate objective is to measure libraries based on many different TFs from several different families (Fig. B9). The pilot-scale experiment is designed to demonstrate the following key capabilities needed for the full-scale data collection:

1. Ability to use the assay to measure multiple different TFs in a single run.
2. Ability to use one set of normalization and calibration sequences for the entire full-scale TF data collection.

The pilot-scale experiment will measure three TF libraries in a single assay run. Normalization and calibration sequences based on RamR and LacI will be used across all libraries. Four concentrations of either zeocin or tetracycline will target overlapping ranges of TF function measurement to optimize antibiotic concentration selection (Fig. B8). Analysis of the data will determine the optimal number of antibiotic concentrations for the full-scale collection; fewer concentrations increase uncertainty but allow more TF libraries per assay run.

Additionally, a single concentration of a ligand/inducer affecting TF-operator interaction will be tested at pilot scale. This will provide mechanistic insights, distinguishing between mutations affecting protein folding and those altering ligand response inversion. The pilot data will assess the value of ligand/inducer measurements compared to measuring more libraries per assay run.

Figure B8: Plate map for the pooled, growth-based assay.

Large-Scale Collection: Expanding Across TF Families

As confidence in these methods increases, we will expand these experiments to include less-characterized proteins from the families used in the pilot-scale experiments. We will also explore additional families as described in (Fig. B9). Each family will be tested with a set of previously-characterized proteins to cross-validate results against existing literature. Additionally, uncharacterized proteins within each family will be tested, divided into two subgroups: those that can be predicted using other methods (e.g., homology data) and those that cannot.

The **TetR family** is one of the largest and most significant in the prokaryotic world, comprising 8.1% of all prokaryotic TFs (from the P2TF Database⁵). Their Helix-Turn-Helix (HTH) binding motif is commonly used by proteins for DNA binding across a wide range of hosts, including bacteria, archaea, and diverse eukaryotes. They bind to a minimal inverted repeat sequence and are small in size, typically between 180 to 250 amino acids.

The **Lacl family** proteins are well-characterized models for allostery. They have an HTH binding motif and are also host agnostic, bind to minimal inverted repeat sequences, and are

medium in size, ranging from 280 to 360 amino acids.

The **zinc finger family**, constituting about 50% of human TFs⁴, is of widespread importance in bioengineering¹⁶. Featuring a distinctive binding motif, they are able to specify a unique sequence in the human genome with less than 170 amino acids. This binding motif makes them a potent tool in both research and therapeutic contexts.

The **MarR family** is in the top eight largest families of prokaryotic TFs and accounts for approximately 4.5% of all prokaryotic TFs (P2TF Database). They have a winged HTH motif, bind to small inverted repeat sequences, and are very small in size, ranging from 150 to 200 amino acids. MarR stands for «multiple antibiotic resistance regulator», as they are implicated in antibiotic resistance⁷.

The **GntR family**, also belonging to the top eight largest families of prokaryotic TFs, comprises about 5.5% of all prokaryotic TFs (P2TF Database). Similar to the MarR family, they also have a winged HTH motif, bind to small inverted repeat sequences, and are relatively small in size, ranging from 230 to 260 amino acids.

Figure B9: Selection strategy for choosing TF targets.

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